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Version 1.0

BMD

Biodiversity Meets Data

D2.3 Access gate to data mobilisation tutorials

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Key takeaway messages

The 'Biodiversity Meets Data (BMD) Access gate to data mobilisation tutorials':

- is released as part of the BMD training portal that is hosted via BMD partner LifeWatch ERIC;
- will, as part of the BMD training portal, be made accessible via BMD's Single Access Point (SAP) as soon as it is released;
- provides access to tutorials that were developed by GBIF, OBIS, PlutoF and COL to support re-use of training materials that are relevant to BMD stakeholders.

Executive summary

Among the expected outcomes of Biodiversity Meets Data (BMD) is ‘A better understanding of the state of nature and of the drivers of biodiversity loss (linked to direct human activity, to climate change, etc..) and of the state of conservation of nature through a better usage of existing data, and through the bridging of data gaps in order to support the implementation of the EU biodiversity strategy for 2030 and therefore to reverse biodiversity loss and to restore and protect ecosystems’. This expected outcome is built on the notion that ‘biodiversity datasets are not sufficiently accessible (too many small, isolated communities of practice, different servers, different data access methods, different formats, rarely accessible through web-services) and too often not well known or advertised outside of their original circle of experts: the access to the results (consolidated data, statistics, maps) of these field surveys should be significantly concentrated behind single entry points’. BMD’s solution is to mobilise these datasets to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility - [GBIF.org](https://www.gbif.org), and the Ocean Biodiversity Information System - [OBIS.org](https://www.obis.org) - for marine and coastal datasets. Importantly, GBIF and OBIS exchange data on marine and coastal biodiversity which is facilitated by the use of common standards with Darwin Core and a shared network of data repositories.

The ‘Introduction’ section describes the different sources of biodiversity data that can be shared with GBIF and OBIS ranging from data derived from museum specimens to environmental DNA samples. All of this data can be shared with GBIF and OBIS. This section also describes GBIF, OBIS and the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) biodiversity data infrastructures in more detail. As these infrastructures have large user communities they have developed a substantial body of training materials to which the BMD provides access via its ‘Access Gate’. The ‘Existing online training materials’ section indicates where different training materials of the respective data portals can be found. A section on mobilising and FAIR storage of the raw eDNA data at ENA is provided as GBIF and OBIS mobilise interpreted species data from eDNA samples. It is important to connect the interpreted data at GBIF and OBIS with the data sources.

For the ‘BMD Access Gate to data mobilisation tutorials’ BMD has selected the LifeWatch ERIC training portal as the most appropriate element of the LifeWatch ERIC infrastructure. Several other European projects use this portal to provide their users and stakeholders with training materials to their products. As our partner LifeWatch is responsible for the BMD Single Access Point (SAP) a seamless integration between the BMD SAP and its Access Gate is embedded in the design. This solution will also support the long-term sustainability of the BMD Access Gate as LifeWatch is an established ERIC and secures the access to training materials beyond the duration of the BMD project.

Non-technical summary

The Biodiversity Meets Data project will provide its stakeholder communities with state of the art high-throughput biodiversity monitoring tools including camera traps, passive acoustic monitoring and eDNA sampling in combination with AI species identification tools. The captured data can then be analysed with co-designed Biodiversity Analysis Tools (BATs) and support effective management of European biodiversity that is protected in the Natura 2000 network. The BATs will include trend analysis tools, the identification of drivers of change, projected impacts of climate change, among others in support of both Natura 2000 site management and the wider biodiversity policy domain in support of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (K-M GBF).

In order to derive trends in the distribution and abundance of species across Europe it is necessary to mobilise historical baseline and legacy biodiversity data. These data are often 'locked' in locally stored databases and Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) reports. To analyse historical baseline data together with the newly generated high-throughput biodiversity data it is necessary to mobilise the data to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) or Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) from where the data is accessible for analysis with the BATs via the Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). Data mobilisation to GBIF and OBIS ensures that the data will be standardised to the Darwin Core (DwC) biodiversity data standard.

BMD can build on a large body of existing tutorials and training materials on the mobilisation of historical baseline and legacy data to the FAIR data portals of GBIF and OBIS. The same applies for the training materials for PlutoF that facilitate the management and mobilisation of eDNA biodiversity data to GBIF, and the Catalogue of Life (COL) that enables the harmonisation of taxonomic names across datasets from different EU member states.

To ensure the long-term sustainability and availability of the 'BMD Access Gate to data mobilisation tutorials' the training portal of LifeWatch ERIC was selected to provide stakeholders and end-users of the BMD tools and services with access to existing training materials via <https://training.lifewatch.eu/international-projects/resources/?category=36> (Fig.12). LifeWatch ERIC is a BMD partner and well-established European Research Infrastructure that remains operational after finalising the BMD project, hence secures the long-term availability of, and access to, the 'BMD Access Gate to data mobilisation tutorials'.

List of abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BAT	Biodiversity Analysis Tool (equivalent to Virtual Research Environment - VRE)
BMD	Biodiversity Meets Data
COL	Catalogue of Life - catalogueoflife.org
DwC	Darwin Core
EEA	European Environment Agency
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EU	European Union
EUNIS	European Nature Information System
GBF	Global Biodiversity Framework (same as K-M GBF)
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility - GBIF.org
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
K-M GBIF	Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (same as GBF)
NRR	Nature Restoration Regulation
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System - OBIS.org
OTGA	Ocean Teacher Global Academy - https://classroom.oceanteacher.org
SAP	Single Access Point
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards (formerly known as Taxonomic Databases Working Group)
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

1. Introduction

For the benefit of people, climate and the planet the EU biodiversity strategy for 2030 - as part of the EU Green Deal - aims to bend the curve of biodiversity loss and provide every opportunity to put Europe's biodiversity on the path to recovery by 2030. This aim will be achieved by a) establishing a coherent and larger EU-wide network of protected areas on land and at sea, b) launch the EU nature restoration regulation, c) enable the necessary transformative change, and d) introducing measures to align with the targets set under the UN Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF). In order to meet these goals there is an urgent need for:

- A. better monitoring of biodiversity by high-throughput methods leading to a better implementation of the nature directives;
- B. a better understanding of the state of nature and of the drivers of biodiversity loss, and of the state of conservation through a better usage of existing data and through the bridging of data gaps; and
- C. a more complete view of the state of nature and its evolution to support policy implementation and policy making.

Biodiversity Meets Data - BMD - responds to these needs by developing a cutting-edge, advanced Single Access Point to an digital toolbox for managers of natural resources, policy-makers and the wider stakeholder landscape. BMD provides access to tools for high-throughput biodiversity monitoring, tools for the mobilisation of base-line and legacy biodiversity data to FAIR data aggregators, and access to relevant spatio-temporal data on environmental and remote sensed habitat data, and past-present-future climatic data for the terrestrial, freshwater and marine realms. The toolbox is equipped with a suite of 'Biodiversity Analysis Tools' (BATs) that are co-designed with the stakeholder community to deliver biodiversity assessments, biodiversity trend analyses, identification of drivers of change, and projections to future climatic and land cover scenarios at local, regional, national and European scales. The tools are essential for the planning, management and expansion of protected areas as they provide near real-time biodiversity monitoring data to assess the conservation status of species and habitats.

In order to detect changes in biodiversity and to identify the drivers of biodiversity change, historical baseline and legacy biodiversity data are essential. BMD targets the need to mobilise base-line and legacy biodiversity data to FAIR data aggregators like the Global Biodiversity Information Facility - [GBIF.org](https://www.gbif.org), the Ocean Biodiversity Information System - [OBIS.org](https://www.obis.org) specifically for marine biodiversity data, and the European Nucleotide Archive - ENA by developing an 'Access Gate to data mobilisation tutorials'. All three organisations have existed for over 10 years, have active user communities and have developed an extensive body of tutorials on data mobilisation. With the establishment of the 'BMD Access Gate to data mobilisation tutorials' we'll provide easy access to existing tutorials. The development of the 'BMD Access Gate' serves as the initial development of the BMD training material portal where the BMD project will gradually add more manuals, tutorials, training documents and videos. Deliverable D2.3

contributes to “BMD objective 2: Provide tools to mobilise historical baseline and legacy biodiversity datasets to FAIR biodiversity data repositories”. Too many datasets are not sufficiently accessible and not well known or advertised outside their original circle of experts and the ‘BMD Access Gate’ will provide users outside the scientific domain with access to relevant existing and novel documentation.

1.1 What is biodiversity data?

Biodiversity data and datasets in the context of BMD refer mainly to species occurrence data that are derived from different sources of truth, or origin, and with different levels of data completeness. In the wider context biodiversity data also includes taxonomy, nomenclature, literature, type specimen information and much more. Species occurrence data consists of (at least) four distinct elements of information that I refer to as the four W’s:

1. taxonomic name - **W**hat organism is it?
2. date - **W**hen was the organism observed or collected?
3. locality - **W**here was the organism observed or collected?
4. person - **W**ho observed, collected and/or identified the organism

1.1.1 Natural History Collection data

Traditionally species occurrence data is derived from natural history museum specimens that were collected over the past 4 centuries. These physical objects are evidence of a once living organism that was collected on a certain date, at a particular locality by a collector and which was subsequently identified by the collector or a taxonomic expert. Older specimens were collected primarily to study the diversity of life on Earth. The concept of evolution did not yet exist, and studying the distribution of plants and animals across the globe was not of main interest. Consequently, locality information of historical specimens is often poor. More recently collected specimens do have geographic coordinates that are collected with a GPS device and allow the precise localisation of specimens. Data from these natural history collections constitutes important baseline data about the historical distribution of species.

1.1.2 Survey data

Next to specimen derived data another source of biodiversity data is represented by vegetation surveys, transect walks and monitoring networks, but also Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs), which provide not only information at the species level but also at the community level. These biodiversity data can be accompanied with measurements of the environment where these communities were observed, e.g. altitude, soil type and pH, salinity, sea surface temperature, etc. that can explain the occurrence of species and the composition of communities. Many datasets that are collected via monitoring programmes remain locked in databases and excel sheets that can be mobilised to public data repositories like GBIF and OBIS. These datasets are the main target for Deliverable 2.3 where BMD provides access to existing data mobilisation tutorials via the BMD Access Gate.

1.1.3 Human observations

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A source of information of biodiversity data that is rapidly growing is based on human observations that are collected via citizen science portals. Initially observations were shared via websites, but since a decade citizen science apps like iNaturalist, Observation.org and eBird collect data with mobile devices which make use of GPS coordinates as locality data. This source of biodiversity information is rapidly growing and constitutes the majority of data points at GBIF¹.

1.1.4 Machine observations

A rapidly increasing source of biodiversity information comes from machines including camera traps, passive acoustic devices, and drones. The BMD project will mainstream this technology and provide wide access to these technologies combined with AI identification platforms to speedup the identification of organisms from images, videos and sound recordings. Providing managers of natural resources, protected areas and specifically Natura 2000 sites should start generating near-real time biodiversity data to support the effective management and protection of species and habitats across Europe.

1.1.5 eDNA samples

Not all domains can be monitored by machines, especially the freshwater and marine realms are challenging although progress is made there as well. The use of environmental DNA, or eDNA, is another technique that can be used to detect specific species, e.g. invasive species, or whole species communities. Mainstreaming the collection of eDNA samples, sequencing, data analysis and data publication to public biodiversity databases is among the core objectives of the BMD project. Through the BMD Access Gate we provide access to tutorials on the mobilisation of eDNA derived biodiversity data to public biodiversity databases.

1.2 Public and open biodiversity databases

There exist many national and international databases and online data portals that provide access to biodiversity data. The downside of these databases is that they often use their own taxonomic concepts and local species names, have different ways of recording locality information, notation of dates, various ways of recording person names, and often use local languages. This makes it very challenging to combine and aggregate these sources of biodiversity information to a European scale. As the BMD project aims to provide biodiversity information and knowledge from local Natura 2000 site level to the continental scale of Europe, it was decided to contribute the newly generated high-throughput biodiversity data, as well as the legacy and historical baseline data, to global and open access biodiversity databases. These databases are supported by a large number of stakeholders and countries and follow internationally accepted biodiversity data standards to facilitate data harmonisation at European and global scales. The biodiversity databases that are supported by BMD are:

- The Global Biodiversity Information Facility - [GBIF.org](https://www.gbif.org)
- The Ocean Biodiversity Information System - [OBIS.org](https://www.obis.org)

¹ https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/search?basis_of_record=HUMAN_OBSERVATION&occurrence_status=present

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- The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration - insdc.org - with three participating databases that mirror their content and provide access to 'more or less' the same resources:
 - [NLM-NCBI](https://nlm-ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/) - National Library of Medicine-National Center for Biotechnology Information - also known as **GenBank**
 - [DDBJ](https://dbj.dna-ri.go.jp/) - DNA Data Base Japan
 - [ENA](https://ena.ebi.ac.uk/) - European Nucleotide Archive - which is most relevant for BMD

1.2.1 The Global Biodiversity Information Facility - GBIF

The Global Biodiversity Information Facility - [GBIF.org](https://gbif.org) - is an international network and data infrastructure funded by the world's governments and aimed at providing anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all types of life on Earth. GBIF was established in 2001² and is currently supported by 44 voting participant countries and 25 associate country participants (February 2026). Europe is represented in GBIF by 24 voting participants and 4 associate country participants³ (Fig.1).

Figure 1: EU country participation in GBIF (February 2026).

GBIF is coordinated through its Secretariat in Copenhagen. The GBIF network of participating countries and organizations provides data-holding institutions and organisations around the world with common standards, best practices and open-source tools enabling them to share information about where and when species have been recorded. GBIF draws these diverse data sources together through the use of

² <https://www.gbif.org/what-is-gbif>

³ <https://www.gbif.org/the-gbif-network/europe>

data standards, including the most important biodiversity data standard the Darwin Core ([Wieczorek et al. 2012](#)). The Darwin Core, or DwC⁴, is maintained by Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) a non-profit organization and a community dedicated to developing biodiversity information standards.

GBIF provides access to more than 3.6 billion biodiversity records (February 2026) of which 1.25 billion occurrence records in Europe⁵. The available records cover all major taxonomic groups but are dominated by the more than 500 million bird occurrence records (Fig.2). Plants are represented by 368 million records, followed by insects 224 million records. GBIF holds 26 million records of European mammals (Fig.2).

Figure 2: European biodiversity records available at [GBIF.org](#) divided over major taxonomic groups (13 December 2025).

⁴ <https://dwc.tdwg.org/>

⁵ <https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/search?continent=EUROPE>

1.2.2 The Ocean Biodiversity Information System - OBIS

The Ocean Biodiversity Information System or OBIS⁶ operates under the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO. OBIS is the world's largest global open-access infrastructure for marine biodiversity data supported by a community of 36 nodes and over 6000 contributors worldwide which deliver interoperable, accessible, high-quality marine biodiversity data and fit-for-purpose, innovative services to support science, policy, and society. OBIS provides access to 167 million marine biodiversity records including data on 203,000 species, 27 million DNA sequences and 313 million measurements and facts that represent additional abiotic data that is collected together with the biodiversity records. Like GBIF, OBIS has implemented the DwC biodiversity data standard.

The data of OBIS can be accessed via⁷:

- A. Mapper - Visual selection and download of smaller subsets
- B. Search - Visual exploration of datasets and taxa (Fig.3)
- C. R package - Programmatic download of smaller subsets and checklists using R
- D. API - Programmatic access to smaller subsets, checklists, and statistics
- E. AWS Open Data - Analysis of large subsets

OBIS Search facilitates searching on Scientific name, Dataset, Common name, Area and Publisher country. Figure 3 shows the results for an area search on the North Sea. The interface provides access to explore the occurrences and to visualise the query results in the Mapper tool.

⁶ <https://obis.org/>

⁷ <https://obis.org/data/access/>

Figure 3: OBIS Search results for the North Sea⁸ (13 December 2025).

Through the implementation of the common DwC biodiversity data standard OBIS and GBIF exchange data on marine biodiversity. At the Living Data 2025 conference in Bogota, Colombia, the partnership between GBIF and OBIS was renewed and they reconfirmed their Joint Strategy for Marine Biodiversity Data (2025-2030)⁹. This collaboration facilitates access to the same marine biodiversity data via both OBIS and GBIF. Additionally to the biodiversity data OBIS uses standard protocols to collect additional abiotic data through the measurements and facts extension.

1.2.3 The European Nucleotide Archive - ENA

The European Nucleotide Archive or ENA¹⁰ is maintained by EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute. ENA is an ELIXIR Core Data Resource representing a set of European data resources of fundamental importance to the wider life-science community and the long-term preservation of biological data. ELIXIR¹¹ is an intergovernmental organisation that brings together life science resources from across Europe. Furthermore, ENA is Global Core Biodata Resource¹² meaning that ENA is considered to be of

⁸ <https://obis.org/area/32350>

⁹ <https://docs.gbif.org/obis-gbif-joint-strategy/en/>

¹⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

¹¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us>

¹² <https://globalbiodata.org/what-we-do/global-core-biodata-resources/>

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fundamental importance to the wider biological and life sciences community and the long term preservation of biological data.

ENA is of great importance to BMD because BMD aims to mainstream biodiversity monitoring using eDNA sampling across Natura 2000 sites in Europe. The raw DNA sequence data, or short read archives, should be deposited in a dedicated database which is represented by ENA as a member of the INSDC. In practice most BMD stakeholders will indirectly interact with ENA when sharing or using eDNA derived biodiversity information via GBIF, OBIS and PlutoF.

PlutoF¹³ is a platform that provides online services to manage your biological data fully integrated and ready for analyses or publishing. PlutoF is developed by Tartu University and provides managers of natural resources with a platform to manage their eDNA data and publish the data to ENA and GBIF so that it can be used in the BMD Biodiversity Analysis Tools for data analysis and reporting purposes.

1.2.4 The Catalogue of Life - COL

The Catalogue of Life (COL) is the most comprehensive initiative to compile a single, integrated list of all known species worldwide¹⁴. COL helps translate expert taxonomic knowledge into a simple to use and understand catalogue that serves researchers, policymakers, environmental managers, and the wider public. Since October 2025 the COL has been assembled from around 17500 instead of from 168 data sources that were originally used, now also including molecular taxonomic data, such as Barcode Index Numbers (BINs) and DNA-based Species Hypotheses. This version is known as the eXtended Release and includes extra data from other sources. The latter is now the default in [catalogueoflife.org](https://www.catalogueoflife.org).

COL is now also suited to taxonomically represent the more than 3,5 billion species occurrences mediated through the Global Biodiversity Information Facility, and to serve as the new taxonomic reference for the occurrences mediated through GBIF. COL is also the taxonomic reference for the European Nature Information System (EUNIS) of the European Environment Agency (EEA). As many EU member states use their own taxonomic lists, BMD will use the COL taxonomy to harmonise taxonomic names across EU member states.

2. Existing online training materials

As described above, public and open biodiversity databases have existed for more than a decade, they have developed an extensive body of training materials and tutorials for the stakeholder communities. The BMD project builds upon, and further strengthens, these initiatives by providing the BMD stakeholder communities including natural resource managers and policy makers with easy access to these materials via the BMD Access Gate. In this section the relevant training materials are identified that will be made accessible via the BMD Access Gate.

¹³ <https://plutof.ut.ee/>

¹⁴ <https://www.catalogueoflife.org/about/catalogueoflife>

2.1 GBIF online training materials

GBIF is the oldest and largest global biodiversity data database. GBIF is an international network and data infrastructure funded by the world's governments and aimed at providing anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all types of life on Earth. The GBIF network of participating countries and organizations, works through the participant nodes, and provides data-holding institutions around the world with common standards, best practices and open-source tools enabling them to share information about where and when species have been recorded. GBIF is a growing organization with new countries joining every year. For that reason new participant nodes need training material that is developed by the GBIF secretariat with the help of the GBIF community. Like the biodiversity data that is accessible through GBIF, also the training materials on how to publish biodiversity data to GBIF is publicly and freely available. Through the membership of many European countries (Fig.1) the BMD project can build on the support of the national GBIF nodes in publishing data from Natura 2000 sites to GBIF. BMD will promote data publication via the GBIF nodes. Managers of Natura 2000 sites from countries that are not a member of GBIF can make use of the 'Europe and Central Asia' - ECA - node¹⁵ that is managed by the GBIF ECA representatives and which is hosted by the GBIF secretariat.

The GBIF portal provides several entries to training materials to which the BMD Access Gate will redirect. The GBIF landing page is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4. GBIF.org landing page.

¹⁵ <https://cloud.gbif.org/eca>

The 'How-to' menu at the top of the landing page provides access to various training resources (Fig.5), including the 'Quick-start guide' and 'Become a publisher' guidelines. In order to publish any dataset at [GBIF.org](https://www.gbif.org) it is required to become a publisher. Endorsement to become a GBIF publisher is important for the following reasons:

1. Published data are relevant to GBIF's scope and objectives
2. Arrangements for data hosting are stable and persistent
3. Data publishing and use are supported by strong national, regional and thematic engagement
4. Data are as open as possible and available for sharing and reuse
5. Data publishers can respond to feedback and improve data quality

Figure 5. The 'How-to' menu of GBIF.

The section on 'Guides and documentation' (Fig.5) gives access to 11 different digital guides that can be used for various purposes. Most of these guides are available in multiple languages.

The largest body of GBIF training materials can be found under menu item 'Community' > 'ACTIVITIES' > 'Training and learning resources' which will redirect to <https://www.gbif.org/training>. This page provides access to GBIF curricula, GBIF Training Courses <https://training.gbif.org/en/>, and Community Resources.

The GBIF curricula section covers five topics (Fig.6). These curricula were developed by the GBIF secretariat together with the GBIF community of trainers and mentors. For the BMD stakeholders the training on 'Introduction to GBIF', 'Biodiversity Data Mobilisation', and 'Accelerating biodiversity research through DNA barcodes, collection and observation data' are most relevant.

Figure 6. The GBIF curricula at <https://www.gbif.org/training>.

The 'Community resources' section provides access to reusable training material and documentation that is developed by the GBIF community, including an overview of upcoming virtual events and workshops via <https://www.gbif.org/resource/search?contentType=event>.

2.2 OBIS Resources

For the marine community OBIS is the dedicated portal to publish biodiversity data. Through a Letter of Agreement marine data from OBIS and GBIF are exchanged. Both infrastructures use the DarwinCore data standard which facilitates the exchange of data. At the OBIS portal under the menu item 'Resources' several manuals, courses and YouTube videos can be found (Fig.7).

Who we are ▾ What we do ▾ Data ▾ Community ▾ Resources ▾ Search

Publications citing OBIS
OBIS manual
OBIS GitHub
OBIS courses on OTGA
DNA derived data publishing
OBIS YouTube

Explore this map

Figure 7. The OBIS 'Resources' menu provides access to training materials at <https://obis.org/>.

The OBIS manual <https://manual.obis.org/> is a very detailed document covering all aspects of marine data and data publishing. For 'OBIS courses on OTGA' (Ocean Teacher Global Academy) it is required to register at the Ocean Expert portal, which is free of costs. OTGA includes a self-paced 'Contribution and publishing datasets to OBIS' training. The option 'DNA derived data publishing' refers to the GBIF manual on this topic, indicative of the good collaboration between GBIF and OBIS. Section 2.3 of the manual is dedicated to 'Marine datasets and the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS). Finally the OBIS YouTube channel provides access to 18 different instruction videos that can be explored.

YouTube NL

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How-To: Using & Publishing Data with ...
by Ocean Biodiversity Information System
Playlist · 19 videos · 2,231 views
This playlist contains step-by-step guides to help you not only format your data for publishing in OBIS but also...more

Play all

- 01 How to construct eventIDs
Ocean Biodiversity Information System · 1k views · 2 years ago
9:43
- 02 Convert coordinates from ddmms to decimal degrees
Ocean Biodiversity Information System · 521 views · 2 years ago
3:55
- 03 How to format eventDate
Ocean Biodiversity Information System · 328 views · 2 years ago
10:48
- 04 How to create and format the Event table for Darwin Core
Ocean Biodiversity Information System · 659 views · 2 years ago
5:52
- 05 How to format the Occurrence table for Darwin Core
Ocean Biodiversity Information System · 801 views · 2 years ago
5:22

Figure 8. The OBIS YouTube channel at https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLlgUwSvpCFS4TS7ZN0fhByj_3EBZ5IXbF

2.3 PlutoF & ENA

BMD provides its stakeholders with access to the PlutoF platform (Fig.9). PlutoF can manage many different data types, but most relevant for the BMD stakeholders are the management tools for eDNA data, the publication of the eDNA-derived taxon occurrence data to GBIF and sample metadata to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) and BioSamples. The menu item 'Documentation' has manuals of the PlutoF platform.

Figure 9. The PlutoF portal at <https://plutof.ut.ee/>.

2.4 COL resources

The COL ChecklistBank tutorial is integrated with the GBIF documentation and can be found at <https://docs.gbif.org/course-checklistbank-tutorial/en/index.en.html>. ChecklistBank is a platform that supports the publication, analysis, and curation of checklists with emphasis in taxonomic and nomenclatural data. It is an integral part of the infrastructure developed and maintained by the Catalogue of Life (COL) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). ChecklistBank provides a repository and a suite of tools to explore its content, and further examine checklists of particular interest.

The online tutorial explains the functionality of the ChecklistBank tools through 4 exercises, including:

1. Explore the **ChecklistBank repository**: search, inspect and download checklists.
2. **Cross dataset search** tool: look up the appearance of a particular scientific name in all data sources available in ChecklistBank.
3. **Name match** tool: enables comparison of the COL Checklist with one or two other datasets in ChecklistBank in terms of taxon name matching.

4. **Dataset comparison** tool: allows for comparison of two taxonomic datasets in ChecklistBank on a scientific name by scientific name basis.

Figure 10. The ChecklistBank tutorial at

<https://docs.gbif.org/course-checklistbank-tutorial/en/index.en.html>.

3. BMD Access Gate to data mobilisation tutorials

Stakeholders are involved in the development of all components of the BMD Single Access Point (SAP) that provides access to the high-throughput biodiversity monitoring tools, tutorials on data mobilisation to GBIF and OBIS, and in the development of the suite of Biodiversity Analysis Tools (BATs). Training, and access to training materials and guideline documents is essential for uptake of the BMD tools. As BMD builds on existing tools and technologies, and makes these tools available to new stakeholder communities, the project can rely on a large body of training materials of the organisations that have developed the tools and technologies, notably GBIF, OBIS, PlutoF and COL as outlined in section ‘2. Existing online training tutorials’. The BMD Access Gate provides stakeholders with links to these tutorials, while at the same time recognising the respective organisations for their contributions.

The ‘BMD Access Gate to data mobilisation tutorials’ is the starting point for the BMD training portal that will become a module of the BMD SAP. As much of the other training materials and course materials will be developed using the LifeWatch training portal we initiated the BMD Access Gate under the ‘International Projects’ menu of the LifeWatch training portal (Fig.11). As BMD partner LifeWatch ERIC is also tasked with the design and development of the BMD SAP, this choice not only ensures seamless integration of the BMD training module with the BMD SAP, but also ensures the long-term sustainability of the BMD SAP and its services, including the training module which at this stage represents the BMD Access Gate.

Figure 11. The LifeWatch ERIC training portal at <https://training.lifewatch.eu/international-projects/> provides access to the BMD training materials.

The BMD Access gate is now available at URL and provides access to the GBIF, OBIS, PlutoF and COL data mobilisation tutorials (Fig.12). The initial BMD Access Gate will gradually be transformed into the BMD training module that will become part of the BMD SAP.

LifeWatch ERIC

Welcome to the BMD Training Platform

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BIODIVERSITY ECAMPUS
USER MANUALS AND TUTORIALS
WEBINARS AND CONFERENCES
INTERNATIONAL PROJECTS
NATIONAL NODES
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ChecklistBank ChecklistBank Tutorial

ChecklistBank is a platform that supports the publication, analysis, and curation of checklists with emphasis in taxonomic and nomenclatural data. It is an integral part of the infrastructure developed and maintained by the Catalogue of Life (COL) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF).

GBIF Training Resources

The GBIF training resources provide access to data mobilisation tutorials covering the widest variety of biodiversity data types and all realms. Marine data at GBIF is exchanged with OBIS.

OBIS OBIS Manual - User Documentation
OCEAN BIOGEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM

The OBIS manual covers the mobilisation of marine biodiversity datasets with special additional attention to abiotic conditions of the biodiversity data to align these with the data requirements of EMODnet.

PlutoF PlutoF Platform - User Documentation

BMD recommends the use of the PlutoF platform for the mobilisation of eDNA datasets to GBIF.

Figure 12. The BMD Training Platform at <https://training.lifewatch.eu/international-projects/resources/?category=36> provides access to training materials that are important to BMD stakeholders.

3.1 The future of the BMD Access Gate

Establishing the ‘BMD Access Gate to data mobilisation tutorials’ at the LifeWatch ERIC training portal is the starting point of the development of the BMD training portal. As BMD develops targeted training materials and tutorials on a) the deployment of high-throughput biodiversity monitoring tools, b) analysis of the data using AI technology, c) mobilising historical baseline and legacy datasets to FAIR biodiversity data infrastructures, and d) each of the Biodiversity Analysis Tools will be added. The BMD Access Gate will gradually transform into the BMD training portal and be made accessible through the BMD SAP that will be delivered towards the end of the project.

4. Acknowledgements

The BMD project acknowledges the services provided by LifeWatch ERIC to facilitate the ‘BMD Access gate to data mobilisation tutorials’ via its training portal. BMD also recognizes the extensive body of training materials and tutorials that was developed by GBIF. The materials provided by GBIF built on over 25 years of development and provide a solid foundation for the ‘BMD Access Gate’. Similarly for the marine realm BMD links to the training portal of OBIS to support the marine stakeholder community.

D2.3 BMD Access gate to data mobilisation tutorials

BMD partner PlutoF has made its infrastructure and training material available to the BMD stakeholder communities which are essential for the management of eDNA data and the sharing of the biodiversity data from eDNA samples with GBIF. Finally BMD wants to thank COL for the development of tutorials on the use of ChecklistBank which is an essential part that is needed for the taxonomic harmonisation across taxonomic lists of EU member states.

